

MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SOCIAL ACTIVITY BASED ON PEDAGOGICAL FACILITATION

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Abstract. This article examines the stages of self-work, forms of self-assessment through self-development, analysis and monitoring in increasing the social activity of students and improving the future professional qualifications of specialists.

Keywords: education, pedagogical, psychological, constructive, productivity, satisfaction, comprehensive development of the individual, honest attitude to work, social activity.

МЕХАНИЗМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ФАСИЛИТАЦИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются этапы самостоятельной работы, формы самооценки через саморазвитие, анализ и контроль в повышении социальной активности студентов и повышении будущей профессиональной квалификации специалистов.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, педагогическое, психологическое, конструктивное, продуктивность, удовлетворенность, всестороннее развитие личности, добросовестное отношение к труду, социальная активность.

New Uzbekistan Development strategy for 2022-2026 Improving state policy on youth. Educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values, able to resist harmful influences and currents, having firm beliefs and views on life. [1]. At the same time, many reforms carried out in our country have also highlighted the need to further improve the professional competence of teachers in improving the quality of professional training of students in the higher education system in the development of civil society on the basis of democratic principles. Being able to withstand the strong competition, which occupies a dominant position in the labor market in the conditions of market relations, indicates the need to have professional competence, consistently increase it from each Specialist. In carrying out these tasks, it is necessary to create effective innovation models based on the principles of multi-level coherence, continuity and consistency in the context of education, to develop professional competences of teachers. Highly qualified in our country on the basis of international standards improving the quality of Teachers ' Training, advanced in the educational process wide implementation of pedagogical technologies and educational programs, continuous social protection of teachers and pedagogical staff in the field of Education and the activities carried out in support of readers it is convenient for them to receive education and for teachers to carry out activities it serves to provide conditions. Also upcoming the processes of professional socialization of primary school teachers there is a need for improvement based on the priority of interactive education. The system of public education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 the quality of the content of the system of continuous education "in the concept of development update in terms of training, as well as training of professional personnel to improve the methodology, to the educational process step-by-step implementation of the principles of individualization"¹ such as important tasks are set.

Having gained independence and experiencing its new development

The process of building a legal and democratic society is successfully carried out in our republic. Further intensification of this process is considered largely due to the mental and moral growth of young people, their physical and mental perfection. The deep acquisition of school education by the pupil-youth ensures that they have the right understanding of the social changes taking place in the society and the content of knowledge, skills and skills necessary to make their contribution at the level of possible.[2]

Today, the process of training teachers is continuous independent learning and social, which are important values of education the role of the factor is incomparable. Here are some of the educational values appears. They are:

1. Organization of social relations in the learning process.
2. Organization of social relations during pedagogical practice.
3. Development of social activity of the future teacher.

It is known that education is a pedagogical relationship between teacher and student is a set of relationships. It is in this relationship that mutual trust, demand and The order is important, that is, knowledge increases, intellect improves. The indicators of the activities of future teachers in the period of pedagogical practice are: productivity, satisfaction, comprehensive development of the individual, honest attitude to work, social activity, valuable direction, etc. It is very important here that the future teacher is satisfied with the emotional-evaluation relationship in his activities, that is, the work he is doing and the conditions for its implementation. An important indicator is the well-being of the socio-psychological environment and the effectiveness of pedagogical activity in the formation of satisfaction from pedagogical labor. We professionalism the teachers of the upcoming primary classes four as criteria for socialization and attitude to professional activity the sphere: motivational, communicative, organizational, personal-professional. Then there are three levels of development of these areas - high,middle, lower levels were identified.

Professional based on these criteria highlight the following levels of socialization possible: a high-level professional who has mastered the necessary qualities directed; have insights into the aftermath of their professional development; has an intermediate level-professional has a basic level of necessary qualities, profession moderately oriented, general about the aftermath of their professional development have cross-sections; development of low-level necessary professional qualities sluggish, lowly career-oriented, after their own professional development was found to have little idea about.

Professional-pedagogical, which will be developed by the future teacher programs of individual development of character are pedagogical, psychological and along with his knowledge of the specialty, he is also one of the following components it is desirable that the composition consists of: didactic skills (cognitive (acoustic) design creative-practical (constructive) research input into communication (communicative) organizational consistency (prosesssual) technicaltechnological skills);

- skills of organizing educational work (cognitive (Gnostic) design skills creative-applied (constructive) research communication input (communicative) organizational consistency feeder (prosesssual) technical and technological skills);

- professional features of the psyche and personal qualities (pedagogical thinking Systematics adaptability mobility creativity present emotional development pedagogical reflection);

- self-development goals and so on assignments, etc.[3]

The work of a specialist on his own can be seen as follows:

- to improve professional BKM;
- critical and creative interpersonal activity;
- achieve professional and creative cooperation;
- development of working capacity;
- eliminate negative habits;
- mastering positive qualities.

- The stage of the teacher's work on his own led to an inseparable, systematic form

the first stage of the course, including-to identify achievements and shortcomings on the basis of an analysis of their activities;

- the second stage-to make a clear decision on enriching achievements and eliminating shortcomings;

The third stage - practical action on the decision search for effective ways of organization; the fourth stage is to try not to repeat mistakes and shortcomings; the fifth stage is the consistent implementation of the decision constant monitoring, etc.

The following practical actions of the teacher reflect his work as a specialist:

- Improving the pedagogical process on the basis of a clear goal, aspiration;
- The effectiveness of the pedagogical process, its own activity increase;
- Consistently updated pedagogical knowledge mastery;
- be aware of advanced technology, methods and tools;
- Effective application of the latest scientific and technical innovations in its activities to reach;
- Improving professional skills and competencies;
- search for measures to prevent, eliminate negative pedagogical conflicts, etc.

Conclusion

In the process of training future teachers in the pedagogical education system, the development of their practical and technological system of professional socialization plays an important role. Based on the content and conclusion of the study conducted in this direction, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. To the skilful pedagogical personality of a renewed society with the relatively increasing demands of teachers, the main part of their-ready to operate in conditions of selfdevelopment Professional Teachers of Pedagogical Sciences
2. future teacher with opportunities for socialization pedagogical conditions of professional formation are sufficient it was noted that the conflicts between the non-creation were not resolved.
3. Pedagogical activity in socialization of student personality the goals are not only in the generalized state, but also in the pedagogical impact special attention to each person who has both the object and the subject care is required, that is, the solution of pedagogical tasks first of all, rely on the individual qualities of the subject of Education the need was determined.
4. Motivation in the professional socialization of the future teacher, will qualities, intellektual potential, emotional qualities, practical the interdependence of skills, selfmanagement capabilities and reflecting the level of socio-cultural activity of the individual individual attributes were identified.

5. The results of our research are general and private-methodical knowledge the relationship between genetic in the occurrence of Occupational formation
6. it was determined that the initial basic function, which is important in terms of size, is to perform.
7. Important in the professional socialization of future teachers significant psychological-pedagogical, specialty, special preparation content selection and structuring pedagogical activity, its functions educational and educational issues, methods of attitude it was determined that it would give an opportunity to have a complete idea of the subject.
8. Modeling of pedagogical activity is general, private and concrete built on the basis of adjectives, in which the teacher is guided and independent education
9. the forms of education associated with obtaining were taken as a basis. In the fashion model necessary professional skills in students based on the integrated methodical system the mechanism of finding adjectives by composition was revealed.
10. The purpose of pedagogical training is professional and personal development such as student self-awareness, assessment and management in the process development of components and in various educational institutions although the preparation to work is counted, the pedagogical category bases the disciplines the main purpose of the study was to study didactic and social activities-whether it should consist in providing psychological adaptation showed.

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